

3D DAMAGE ANALYSIS APPLIED TO LOW-ENERGY IMPACTS ON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Low-velocity impacts on carbon-epoxy laminates result in local damage; the integrity of aircraft structures when subjected to these impacts is currently assessed via experimental analysis. This study aims at numerically simulating the damage appearance in order to calculate the post-impact remaining load-carrying capabilities of impacted structures. Therefore, a mechanical and numerical modelling of the damage occurring in laminates, previously defined at LMT [1] [8], is updated to this specific type of loading. A rich experimental data base on laboratory specimens enables thorough comparisons between model simulations and experimental results. Preliminary results show good correlation with qualitative experimental characterization and emphasizes a high sensibility of the results towards calculation accuracy.

KEYWORDS: Low-velocity impact, carbon-epoxy laminated composites, Damage Mechanics, delamination

INTRODUCTION

In aircraft applications, the increasing demand for light-weight, high-strength structures has resulted in the intensive use of laminated composite materials for structural components. Attention is focussed here on the integrity of these structures when subjected to low-energy, low-velocity impacts from dropped tools during maintenance and from runaway stones during landings and take-offs. The design of these structures and the prediction of the evolution of impact damage during aircraft service is currently based on material data obtained from drop-weight tests on material samples and on full-size components; experimental damage characterizations are used as input data for post-impact calculations within the frameworks of Linear Elastic Rupture Mechanics [11].

This study aims at numerically simulating the birth of impact-initiated damage for given incident energies, in order to assess the remaining load-carrying capabilities of impacted structures with minimal experimental tests. The intensive experiments conducted at CCR (Centre Commun de Recherches Louis Blériot, Aérospatiale) offers facilities for comparing numerical

simulations with relevant experimental data, and enables an accurate understanding of impact damage mechanisms. Strong interactions occur between transverse cracking and delamination, which makes post-impact calculations highly dependant on the quality of damage prediction. In the range of velocities considered, the validity of quasi-statics was checked against experimental comparisons between drop-weight tests and indentation tests.

In regards to the physics of damage in laminates submitted to low-velocity impacts, we intend to use a damage meso-model developed at LMT [1] [8] (Laboratoire de Mécanique et de Technologie, Ecole Normale Supérieure de Cachan), which already includes both transverse cracking and delamination. Nevertheless, new aspects like localized loading, coupling between different damage mechanisms, and high influence of out-of-plane stresses ask for specific développements discussed here.

DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION

Post-impact tests show strong interactions between the level of damage of the impacted structure and its residual strength, both for in-plane traction loading, where fiber breakage plays a significant role, and for in-plane compression loading, which emphasizes the primary importance of delaminations leading to local buckling.

Quantitative damage characterization

As we intend to perform post-impact characterization of laminated structures, any impact simulation should correlate with experimentally measured post-impact damaged configuration. Aérospatiale developed a special double-transmission echo ultrasonic control scanning set-up, enabling visualisation of through-the-thickness delaminated areas by distance and amplitude analysis of the ultrasonic echo. The regular increase of delaminated areas through the thickness from impacted side to non-impacted side, and the use of $[90^0, \dots, 90^0 - i * (45^0), \dots]_s$ lay-ups with regular rotation from one ply to the other, makes it possible to obtain the delaminated area per interface.

Qualitative damage characterization

CCR experimental observations and other correlating studies [5] [6], lead to the following precepts, which form the base of the study:

- damage mechanisms involved are the same in impact tests as those encountered in statics [6]; inertial and vibration effects are relatively insignificant;
- transverse cracking is precursive to delamination [10]; transverse cracks grow parallel to the fibers, symmetrically with the impact point, creating in each ply bands released in the normal direction. Throughout the laminate thickness, these cracks depict a typical conical shape with the smaller base on the impacted side; throughout the ply thickness, the slope of the transverse cracks propagating between fibre-matrix decohesions observed on MEB [3] images gives evidence to the influence of transverse shear stresses;
- delaminations propagate in an area delimited by these released bands, whose normal displacements create both an interfacial tractional normal stress field and a compressive one, with a typical double-triangular shape, as depicted in Figure (1).
- indentation is a source of local fibre breakage; this damage mode is of minor importance in regards with the criticality of delamination micro-buckling effects.

Figure 1: "double-triangular" mechanism

DAMAGE MESOMODELLING

These qualitative damage observations were used as a base for qualitative comparison with simulations with the LMT Damage Mesomodel [1] [8]. Regarding the first results, the following updates were performed to improve the physical relevance of the model:

- the influence of out-of-plane ply stresses on ply damage forces were not taken into account; the ply strain energy has been re-formulated (see §Ply modelling);
- the anti-delaminating effect of compressive interfacial normal stresses was not taken into account; a new coupling between interface damage forces and the compressive normal stress has been introduced (see §Interface modelling).

Furthermore, the highly localized distribution of pressure under the impactor raises new specific questions about the load modelling (see §load modelling) and the calculation accuracy (see §computational tool).

Ply modelling [8]

G_{12} (elastic shear modulus) and E_2 (transverse traction elastic modulus) are the only moduli affected by ply damage (fibre-matrix decohesion and transverse cracking). Two damage variables, d_{ps} for G_{12} , and d_{pt} for E_2 , represent local rigidity losses. Therefore, the strain energy is formulated as follows:

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{aligned} & \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_+^2}{E_1^0} + \gamma \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle_-^2}{E_1^0} - \frac{\nu_{12}^0 \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22}}{E_1^0} + \dots \\ & + \frac{1}{1-d_{pt}} \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_+^2}{E_3^0} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+^2}{E_2^0} \right) + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_-^2}{E_2^0} + \dots \\ & + \frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_-^2}{E_3^0} + \frac{1}{1-d_{ps}} \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{G_{13}^0} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0} \right) + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{G_{13}^0} \end{aligned} \right) \quad (1)$$

where 1 is the fibre direction, 3 the normal direction, $\langle \sigma_{ii} \rangle_-$ the compressive part of σ_{ii} , $\langle \sigma_{ii} \rangle_+$ its traction counterpart and γ is a coefficient devoted to the representation of the non-symmetry of the ply behaviour under tensile loading in the fibre direction.

A coupling between thermodynamic quantities associated to d_{ps} and d_{pt} , called thermodynamic forces or damage forces, respectively $Y_{d_{ps}}$ et $Y_{d_{pt}}$, is introduced via two material constants, b_s and b_t which represent interactions between damage modes.

$$Y_{d_{ps}} = \left(\frac{\delta E_D}{\delta d_{ps}} \right)_{d_{pt}} = \frac{[[\sigma_{12}]]^2}{2G_{12}^0 (1-d_{ps})^2} + \frac{[[\sigma_{13}]]^2}{2G_{13}^0 (1-d_{ps})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{d_{pt}} = \left(\frac{\delta E_D}{\delta d_{pt}} \right)_{d_{ps}} = \frac{[[\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+^2]]}{2E_2^0(1-d_{pt})^2} + \frac{[[\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_+^2]]}{2E_3^0(1-d_{pt})^2} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_{ps} = Y_{d_{ps}} + b_s Y_{d_{pt}} \text{ et } Y_{pt} = Y_{d_{pt}} + b_t Y_{d_{ps}} \quad (4)$$

where $[[X]]$ is the mean value of X through the ply thickness.

As usual, evolution laws for the internal damage variables are taken as follows:

$$d_{ps} = \frac{\sqrt{Y_{ps}} - \sqrt{Y_{ps0}}}{\sqrt{Y_{psc}}} \text{ for } \begin{cases} d_{ps} < 1 \\ d_{pt} < 1 \\ Y_{ps} < Y_{psf} \end{cases} ; d_{pt} = \frac{\sqrt{Y_{pt}} - \sqrt{Y_{pt0}}}{\sqrt{Y_{ptc}}} \text{ for } \begin{cases} d_{ps} < 1 \\ d_{pt} < 1 \\ Y_{pt} < Y_{ptf} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where Y_{ps0} , Y_{psc} and Y_{psf} are respectively the initiation, critical and fragile thresholds for shear damage and Y_{pt0} , Y_{ptc} and Y_{ptf} the initiation, critical and fragile thresholds for transverse traction damage.

With such a modified formulation of the strain energy, there is no need for new material constants in the model, which enables the use of existing experimental procedures developed in [9], based on classical tests of Rupture Mechanics.

Interface modelling [1]

σ_{33} , σ_{23} and σ_{13} are stresses associated to interfacial displacement discontinuities in direction 3 (normal direction), direction 2, and direction 1 (defined as the bisectrix of the fibre directions of the adjacent plies). Relative elastic moduli are k_3^0 , k_2^0 and k_1^0 , respectively affected by internal damage variables d_3 , d_2 and d_1 , related to opening modes 1, 2, and 3. Therefore, strain energy is formulated as follows:

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_-^2}{k_3^0} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_+^2}{k_3^0(1-d_3)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{23} \rangle_+^2}{k_2^0(1-d_2)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{13} \rangle_+^2}{k_1^0(1-d_1)} \right) \quad (6)$$

In the same way as for plies, thermodynamic forces Y_{d_3} , Y_{d_2} and Y_{d_1} associated to d_3 , d_2 and d_1 are derived from E_d , and coupling between the different modes is introduced via material constants α , γ_1 and γ_2 ; attention is drawn to a new coupling between the thermodynamical forces and the anti-delaminating influence of compressive interfacial normal stress, via a new material constant χ .

$$Y_{d_3} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_-^2}{k_3^0(1-d_3)^2} \right); Y_{d_1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{k_1^0(1-d_1)^2} \right); Y_{d_2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{k_2^0(1-d_2)^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$Y_d = (Y_{d_3}^\alpha + \gamma_1 Y_{d_1}^\alpha + \gamma_2 Y_{d_2}^\alpha)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - \chi \frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle_-}{k_3^0} \quad (8)$$

An isotropic damage evolution law gives:

$$d_1 = d_2 = d_3 = \frac{n}{n+1} \left(\frac{\langle Y_d \rangle_+}{Y_c} \right)^n \text{ si } d < 1, d = 1 \text{ sinon.} \quad (9)$$

where Y_c is a critical threshold for interfacial damage. It is of interest to notice that a $n = 1$ choice enables classical Linear Elastic Rupture Mechanics correlations.

Experimental identification procedures for the interface model [2] have to be updated to take

into account the new material constant χ .

Load modelling

Surface pressure distribution under the indenter, therefore volume stress distribution in the plies under the indenter, conditions the location of indentation fibre breakage. As there is no complete analytical solution for this anisotropic contact problem, we use Hertz theory modified for transversely isotropic half-spaces [4], with the hypothesis of rigid body for the indenter:

$$R_{cont} = \left(\frac{3Q R_1 (1 - \nu_1^2)}{4E_H} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (10)$$

$$P_{max} = \frac{3Q}{2\pi R_{cont}^2} \quad (11)$$

$$P(x, y) = P_{max} \left(1 - \frac{x^2 + y^2}{R_{cont}^2} \right) \quad (12)$$

where R_{cont} is the contact radius of the contact surface, R_1 the indenter radius, P_{max} the maximum pressure under the indenter, $P(x, y)$ its distribution, and E_H a Hertz rigidity coefficient.

Considering the laminate plate behaviour as varying from the half-space one, E_H is to be modified to take flexure into account. We use the non-penetrability condition between plate and indenter to get the correction on E_H at maximum load, and use it as a constant value for E_H on the whole loading history.

COMPUTATIONNAL TOOL

To solve the 3D non-linear evolution problem, an in-house software is used, DSDM [1] (Delamination Simulation by Damage Mechanics), dedicated primarily to the analysis of laminated plates with a central hole and submitted to in-plane loadings. Specific numerical difficulties, related to the highly localized out-of-plane stresses transferring from plies to interfaces, require some special developpements, which are still under progress at present.

To avoid a 3D analysis over the whole-structure, only the damageable area circling the impact point is analysed via a two-step procedure:

- a 2D elastic calculation evaluates the displacements U_d along a circle surrounding the impact zone;
- the 3D non-linear calculations are restricted to the volume inside this circle, with a link to the 3D solution through given displacements U_d along the circle.

The use of a circular line for linking with the 2D plate solution enables one to reduce the volume analysis to series of 2D problems in orthoradial strips by means of a Fast-Fourier-Transform of the 3D problem.

A non-incremental numerical sheme is used to perform the non-linear calculations. It proceeds in iterative projections on the whole loading history from local solutions (satisfying the material non-linear behaviour at each Gauss point) to global solutions (satisfying the whole-structure equilibrium and boundary conditions). Iterations are stopped when a convergence criterion is satisfied, based on the "Error in constituive Relation" concept [7], which measures global energetic mismatches between local and global solutions.

Postprocessing offers possibilities of analysing the results with damage, stress and strains mappings in selected plies, interfaces or orthoradial strips planes, and the evolutions of these quantities with respect to time at selected Gauss points.

RESULTS

Before simulating actual cases of aircraft structures submitted to impacts, a basic case has been studied to check the ability of the model to represent the "double-triangular" shape mechanism. A $(0^0, 45^0)$ lay-up plate was considered, with a 175X150X2.1 mm shape, made of T300/914 carbon/epoxy material, simply supported along a rectangular line of 150X125 mm dimensions, submitted to a maximal transverse 200 N load by a spherical ϕ 16 mm indenter.

Simulated damage configuration in the 45^0 bottom ply is shown in Figure (2), both for shear damage d_{ps} (2a) and for transverse traction damage d_{pt} (2b). Though the transferring of stresses is well depicted (2c and 2d), a high sensibility of interfacial damage towards the "Error in Constitutive Relation" indicator is observed. This numerical behaviour is specific to the highly localized damage phenomena, and requires improvements in convergence efficiency of DSDM software for cases with more degrees of freedom. An impact simulation for a $(-45^0, 0^0, 45^0, 90^0)_s$ lay-up laminate, for which we have experimental damage characterization at disposal, is under progress.

Figure 2: Damage results

CONCLUDING REMARKS

As for modelling relevance, early simulations of a basic impact case are encouraging. Attention has to be focussed now on numerical improvements of the software to ensure calculation accuracy and speed. Simulations of actual impact cases are in progress.

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